

DRIVE THEORY OF EFFECTIVE SCHOOL LEADERSHIP

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ABSTRACT

Effective school leadership is a pivotal factor in the success of educational institutions. This study sought to generate a theory on effective school leadership using a deductive axiomatic approach, following the steps outlined by Padua (2012). The axioms underpinning this study were derived from extensive literature review and empirical evidence. Five core axioms had been identified: Effective school leaders are (1) visionary; (2) conversationalists; (3) good instructors; (4) efficient resource managers; and (5) adaptable to changes. From these axioms, five propositions were formulated to further elaborate the theory of effective school leadership: School leaders (1) articulate a clear, future-oriented vision and communicate it effectively with all stakeholders; (2) provide instructional support and maintain open communication with teachers about teaching strategies to enhance student academic performance; (3) ensure the optimal utilization of resources, directing them towards achieving the school's goals and objectives; (4) adapt innovative instructional practices and support teachers' professional development to improve student achievement; and (5) foster a positive culture of open communication among teachers and efficiently manage financial, human, and material resources. These propositions culminate in the Dynamic-Resourceful-Instructional-Visionary-Engaging (D.R.I.V.E.) Theory of Effective School Leadership. This theory emphasizes the integration of dynamic adaptability, resourceful management, instructional competence, visionary thinking, and engaging communication as key elements in fostering a successful educational environment. The implications of this study highlight the need for effective

leadership practices that enhance educational outcomes, inform policy reforms to support leadership development, and encourage further exploration of existing theories. By adopting this framework, policymakers, educational institutions, and leadership training programs can enhance the effectiveness of school leaders, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes and student success.

Keywords: *effective school leadership, educational success, deductive axiomatic approach*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is a critical factor in the success and effectiveness of any organization, influencing its direction, culture, and outcomes (Pont, 2020; Norbu & Norbu, 2021). Effective leadership involves guiding and motivating individuals toward achieving common goals, adapting to changing environments, and fostering an atmosphere of collaboration and innovation. Within the realm of education, this general understanding of leadership takes on a unique dimension, focusing specifically on the role of school leaders.

School leadership, encompassing administrative, instructional, and community engagement roles, is essential in creating positive school climates, enhancing student achievement, and improving teacher satisfaction. It is widely recognized as a critical factor for school effectiveness and student outcomes (Norbu & Norbu, 2021). This multifaceted role requires a deep understanding of various domains to effectively guide schools toward achieving their educational goals (Ross & Cozzens, 2016; Wahlstrom, 2008). As schools face increasing demands to improve academic performance, the importance of effective school leadership has become a priority in educational research and practice (Leithwood et al., 2008).

The importance of school leadership is underscored by numerous studies across different countries (Ross & Cozzens, 2016; Wahlstrom, 2008; Norbu & Norbu, 2021). Research indicates that strong leadership directly influences educational outcomes by setting a clear vision, fostering a collaborative culture, and implementing evidence-based practices. Effective leaders are pivotal in creating an environment that supports learning and growth, extending their impact beyond administrative duties to the overall school culture and community trust in the education system (Ross & Cozzens, 2016; Wahlstrom, 2008). Effective leadership for productive schools involves establishing a vision for learning, developing strong instructional and curricular programs, implementing assessment strategies, fostering communities of learning, allocating resources effectively, and promoting an organizational culture conducive to success (Murphy et al., 2010; Pashiardis & Johansson, 2020; Norbu & Norbu, 2021; Pillsbury, 2014).

Furthermore, leaders must demonstrate core competencies such as decision-making, communication, and relationship-building to cultivate a healthy school climate that

empowers teachers and supports student achievement (Ross & Cozzens, 2016; Goddard & Miller, 2010). Hence, effective school leadership is a blend of administrative, instructional, and community-oriented roles. One framework for understanding the dimensions of effective school leadership identifies eight key areas: vision for learning, instructional program, curricular program, assessment program, communities of learning, resource allocation and use, organizational culture, and social advocacy (Murphy et al., 2010). Principals who demonstrate competence in these areas are better equipped to drive school improvement and student achievement (Ross & Cozzens, 2016).

The vision for learning articulated by the school leader sets the tone for the entire institution. Effective leaders can clearly communicate a shared vision for student success and rally the school community around this common purpose. They also play a critical role in shaping the instructional program, ensuring that teaching and learning practices are aligned with the school's vision and target academic outcomes (Murphy et al., 2010). Another key dimension of effective school leadership is the leader's ability to cultivate a positive organizational culture (Ross & Cozzens, 2016). Principals who foster a climate of trust, collaboration, and continuous improvement are more likely to see sustainable gains in school performance (Murphy et al., 2010).

Part of this work involves strategically allocating resources, both human and material, to support the school's instructional priorities (Murphy et al., 2007). Effective school leaders also recognize the importance of building strong communities of learning, which include not just the school faculty and staff but also parents, students, and the broader community. By reaching out to stakeholders and actively involving them in the educational process, leaders can leverage these partnerships to enhance student learning and school improvement efforts (Aidman & Baray, 2016). School leaders must be adept at social advocacy, using their platform to champion the needs of their school community and advocate for the resources and support required to fulfill their educational mission. Effective school leaders recognize that their role extends beyond the confines of the school walls, requiring them to actively engage with policymakers, community organizations, and other stakeholders to secure the necessary support and funding to drive school improvement and deliver high-quality education to all students (Murphy et al., 2010). This multifaceted role demands a diverse skillset and deep commitment to student success, as leaders must navigate complex political and social landscapes while maintaining a relentless focus on equity and the success of every child in their care.

However, the landscape of school leadership is continually evolving, shaped by technological advancements, policy reforms, and societal changes (Ross & Cozzens, 2016; Wahlstrom, 2008; Norbu & Norbu, 2021). Today's school leaders face a myriad of challenges, including addressing diverse student needs, managing limited resources, and navigating the complexities of educational policies and standards (Ross & Cozzens, 2016; Goddard & Miller, 2010; Norbu & Norbu, 2021).

Globally, the concept of effective school leadership is universally recognized, though its specific traits and practices can vary. Nonetheless, the core competencies and behaviors that define successful school leadership remain consistent, underscoring the critical

importance of this role in the educational landscape. In the United States, for instance, school principals are expected to exhibit a range of leadership skills that encompass various aspects of school management and improvement. They are responsible for demonstrating curricular expertise, analyzing data to inform decision-making, effectively managing resources, and engaging with the broader school community. These competencies are crucial for principals to drive student achievement and create a positive learning environment (Döş & Savaş, 2015). Similarly, in the context of Sabah, Malaysia, the leadership competencies of school principals are emphasized as a key factor in enhancing school effectiveness and efficiency. Principals are expected to possess strong management and organizational skills, a high level of commitment to their work, and the ability to lead their school in navigating the complex and rapidly changing educational landscape (Silam et al., 2021).

In the United Kingdom, effective school leaders are expected to drive school improvement initiatives, engage with diverse stakeholders, and create positive school cultures that foster academic excellence. They are expected to demonstrate strong instructional leadership, strategic decision-making, and a commitment to continuous professional development for themselves and their teaching staff (Marasan et al., 2021). In Australia, school leaders are required to exhibit a range of competencies that align with the Australian Professional Standard for Principals (Marasan et al., 2021). These standards encompass strategic leadership, instructional leadership, and the ability to engage with the broader community to support student learning and wellbeing. Singapore, renowned for its high-performing education system, selects school leaders based on rigorous criteria and provides extensive training through programs like the Leaders in Education Program (LEP). Singaporean principals are expected to be visionary, innovative, and adept at fostering a collaborative school culture that empowers teachers and students alike (Jayapragas, 2016).

In the context of the Philippines, the importance of school leadership is particularly pronounced given the diverse and complex educational landscape. The development and practice of school leadership in the Philippines is shaped by a rich history that has influenced policy and education in the country (Sutherland & Brooks, 2013). The Philippine education system faces unique challenges, such as varying levels of resource availability, disparities in educational access, and the need to address multilingual and multicultural student populations. Effective school leaders in the Philippines must navigate these complexities while striving to create equitable and high-performing learning environments. The country's recent educational reforms, including the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (K-12), have emphasized the critical role of school principals in driving positive change (Generelao et al., 2022; Sutherland & Brooks, 2013). Moreover, the decentralization of educational governance in the Philippines (Saguin & Ramesh, 2020) has necessitated a stronger focus on building the capacities of school leaders to lead change and drive improvements at the local level.

Across these different educational contexts, it consistently highlights the central role of school leaders in shaping the overall success of a school and several characteristics emerge in effective school leadership. Key traits such as instructional leadership,

strategic vision, and strong communication skills are universally essential. However, contextual differences, such as policy environments, resource availability, and cultural factors, influence the specific practices and challenges faced by school leaders in each country.

Existing theories of effective school leadership offer diverse perspectives on what constitutes successful leadership in educational settings, each with its strengths and limitations. One prominent framework for understanding effective school leadership is the Pashiardis-Brauckmann Holistic Leadership Framework which highlights the multidimensional nature of effective school leadership (Pashiardis & Johansson, 2020). However, some scholars argue that this approach may be overly broad and complex. They contend that a more targeted focus on specific leadership behaviors and practices may be more impactful in fostering productive schools. Some researchers emphasize the importance of instructional leadership, where principals actively engage in shaping the instructional program, providing guidance and support to teachers, and ensuring the effective delivery of curricula and assessments. Rather than spreading their attention across multiple domains, these leaders maintain a focused emphasis on strengthening the core instructional practices within their schools (Murphy et al., 2010). In contrast, the theory of transformational school leadership posits that effective leaders must go beyond just managing instruction and instead work to inspire and motivate their staff, cultivating a shared vision and commitment to school improvement (Leithwood & Slegers, 2006). These transformational leaders seek to empower and develop their teachers, fostering a collaborative culture of continuous learning and innovation. Despite the leader's ability to inspire and motivate followers, some scholars argue that this approach may not be sufficient on its own for effective school leadership. They contend that a more targeted focus on specific leadership behaviors and practices, such as instructional leadership, may be more impactful in fostering productive schools.

The exploration of effective school leadership remains a vital area of research despite the existence of established theories due to several theoretical gaps. First, many existing theories often focus on specific aspects of leadership, such as instructional practices or transformational qualities, without fully integrating the dynamic and multifaceted nature of school environments. This can lead to a narrow understanding of what constitutes effective leadership in diverse educational contexts. Additionally, existing theories may not adequately address the unique challenges faced by schools in developing countries, where resource limitations, cultural differences, and varying stakeholder expectations significantly impact leadership effectiveness. Furthermore, while some theories emphasize adaptability or collaboration, they may lack a comprehensive framework that synergizes all critical leadership elements. The rapid changes in educational landscapes, influenced by technology, societal shifts, and policy reforms, necessitate a fresh theoretical perspective that encapsulates these evolving dynamics.

Also, a significant gap exists between theoretical knowledge and the practical application of leadership principles there are many educational institutions grapple with leadership deficiencies that impede their progress. Many school leaders lack the training and support necessary to excel in their roles, resulting in suboptimal educational outcomes. This gap

in practical application is a pressing issue, as ineffective leadership can lead to a decline in teacher morale, increased staff turnover, and diminished student performance. These challenges not only affect the immediate school environment but also have broader societal implications, including reduced community trust in the education system and limited opportunities for student success beyond school. This gap highlights the necessity for research that not only understands the local context but also provides actionable insights for school leaders operating within these unique environments.

Research Questions

This study aimed to establish and formulate a theory on effective school leadership, which captures the desired characteristics and practices of school leaders that make them successful. Specifically, this theory generation aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What theory can be generated based on axioms and propositions?
 2. What recommendations for future theory validation can be proposed?
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METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the process of deduction in theory development. Deductive research approach explores a known theory or phenomenon and tests if that theory is valid in given circumstances. It has been noted that the deductive approach follows the path of logic most closely. The reasoning starts with a theory and leads to a new hypothesis. This hypothesis is put to the test by confronting it with observations that either lead to a confirmation or a rejection of the hypothesis (Si-Rajab et al., 2019; Lee & Chi-Shing, 2017). Moreover, deductive reasoning can be explained as reasoning from the general to the particular in a top-down manner (Pashiardis & Johansson, 2020). Specifically, the deduction process was done through the deductive axiomatic approach to generate the theory on effective school leadership.

According to Novikov (2011), the axiomatic approach is a way of arriving at a scientific theory in which certain primitive assumptions are postulated as the basis of the theory, while the remaining of the theory are obtained as consequences of these assumptions. The primitive assumptions are called axioms, and the consequences of these axioms are the propositions. These propositions are put to test through using appropriate methodology with specific data. When these propositions are accepted, then the generated theory must be accepted (Trochim, 2006; Zalaghi and Khazaei, 2016).

The steps that the paper follows are reflective of the deductive axiomatic approach in generating the theory (Padua, 2012), as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Deductive Axiomatic Approach in Theory Development
(Adapted from Padua, 2012)

Choosing the Phenomenon of Interest. The initial step in developing the theory involved identifying effective school leadership as the phenomenon of interest. This encompassed various underlying events and dynamics that contributed to successful leadership practices within educational institutions, reflecting reliable observations (University of Minnesota Libraries Publishing, 2010).

Reading the Literature. Once effective school leadership was selected as the focus, a comprehensive review of related literature was conducted. The literature search was a systematic process designed to capture all relevant studies on the effectiveness of various leadership approaches in enhancing school performance. This involved developing a robust search strategy that identified key databases such as Science Direct, Google Scholar, ProQuest, and ERIC (Educational Resources Information Center).

The researchers carefully selected search terms and keywords, utilizing Boolean operators to refine the search for greater specificity. By employing operators like AND, OR, and NOT, the search process became more precise. Additionally, the researchers used double quotation marks and parentheses to indicate the order of search terms, ensuring that results aligned closely with the focus of effective school leadership. Specifically, the researchers implemented the AND operator along with double quotation marks to guide the databases in discovering relevant studies effectively. The search terms included combinations such as ("Effective School Leadership" OR "School Leadership Theories" OR "Transformational Leadership") AND ("Student Achievement" OR "School Improvement" OR "Educational Outcomes") AND ("Leadership Practices" OR "Leadership Strategies").

This thorough approach clarified the specific elements defining effective leadership—such as dynamic adaptability and resourceful management—while enhancing the research methodology. Expanding the knowledge base was crucial for theory generation, as it informed the formulation of relevant axioms and propositions (Kumar, 2011). Ultimately, this comprehensive body of literature aimed to inform the development of the theory and enhance the understanding of effective leadership practices in diverse educational contexts.

Brainstorming. Following the literature review, the researcher engaged in a brainstorming phase to explore various aspects of effective school leadership. This involved analyzing diverse perspectives and contextual factors that influence leadership practices in different educational settings. The brainstorming process was crucial for generating insights into the complexities of school leadership, allowing for a deeper understanding of how different variables interact within the leadership landscape. By examining various dimensions, the researcher was able to identify key ideas that informed the development of appropriate axioms for the theory (Mickenberg, 2017).

Formulating Assumptions (Axioms) and Propositions. The insights gained from the brainstorming sessions were synthesized into foundational axioms and propositions. Axioms serve as the fundamental assumptions that underlie the theory, such as the necessity of dynamic adaptability in leadership, which highlights the importance of flexibility in response to changing school environments and challenges. Propositions, on the other hand, articulate the consequences derived from these axioms, illustrating how specific leadership practices impact educational outcomes. For instance, the relationship between resourceful management and instructional competence emphasizes how effective allocation of resources can enhance teaching quality and student achievement (Novikov, 2011).

Theory Construction. The final step involved constructing the theory by interrelating the propositions and articulating them in general terms. This process resulted in a cohesive framework that defined effective school leadership through interconnected concepts, definitions, and propositions. By systematically linking the various components, the theory provided a logical view of how different leadership elements interact and collectively contribute to overall school effectiveness. This structured approach not only clarified the relationships among the core elements of effective leadership but also offered a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play within educational institutions (Kerlinger, 1986).

RESULTS

The phenomenon investigated in this study is the development of effective school leadership within K-12 schools in the Philippines. Effective school leadership is vital for shaping educational outcomes, improving student achievement, teacher satisfaction, and overall school performance amidst persistent challenges such as low academic performance, high dropout rates, and uneven resource distribution. Leaders in these diverse environments must navigate socio-economic disparities and cater to the diverse needs of students while implementing recent educational reforms like the K-12 system and adapting to changing curriculum standards. This research aims to identify the key traits, strategies, and behaviors that define effective school leaders in the Philippine context, examining how they address these challenges and utilize support mechanisms to enhance their leadership effectiveness.

Literature review and brainstorming lead the researcher to formulate statements, which are regarded to be established, accepted, and self-evidently true. These statements or

axioms are as follows: Effective school leaders are (1) visionary; (2) conversationalists; (3) good instructors; (4) efficient resource managers; and (5) adaptable to changes. The formulation of the five axioms further leads to the formulation of five propositions. These propositions are as follows: School leaders (1) articulate a clear, future-oriented vision and communicate it effectively with all stakeholders; (2) provide instructional support and maintain open communication with teachers about teaching strategies to enhance student academic performance; (3) ensure the optimal utilization of resources, directing them towards achieving the school's goals and objectives; (4) adapt innovative instructional practices and support teachers' professional development to improve student achievement; and (5) foster a positive culture of open communication among teachers and efficiently manage financial, human, and material resources. These axioms and propositions formulated are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Formulated Axioms and Propositions

Axioms	Propositions
1. Effective school leaders are visionary.	1. School leaders articulate a clear, future-oriented vision and communicate it effectively with all stakeholders.
2. Effective school leaders are conversationalist.	2. School leaders provide instructional support and maintain open communication with teachers about teaching strategies to enhance student academic performance.
3. Effective school leaders are visionary.	3. School leaders ensure the optimal utilization of resources, directing them towards achieving the school's goals and objectives.
4. Effective school leaders are visionary.	4. School leaders adapt innovative instructional practices and support teachers' professional development to improve student achievement.
5. Effective school leaders are visionary.	5. School leaders foster a positive culture of open communication among teachers and efficiently manage financial, human, and material resources.

DISCUSSION

Axiom 1: Effective school leaders are visionary. Visionary school leadership extends beyond simply crafting an aspirational vision statement (Muhammad et al., 2019). Rather, it requires principals to actively involve teachers and staff in the visioning process, building buy-in and a shared sense of purpose (Waluyo et al., 2020). Principals, who

demonstrate strong leadership skills and a visionary mindset, are crucial for guiding their schools towards ambitious academic, social, and organizational goals (Murphy et al., 2010). They possess a keen ability to identify future opportunities that can drive organizational advancement (Muhammad et al., 2019). These visionary leaders are able to cultivate a clear and compelling vision for their schools, guiding their institutions towards ambitious academic and social goals (Gunawan et al., 2020). By articulating a bold and forward-looking vision, visionary principals can inspire their communities, mobilize resources, and steer their schools towards meaningful progress and lasting impact. Hence, it is assumed that effective school leaders are visionary.

Proposition 1. School leaders articulate a clear, future-oriented vision and communicate it effectively with all stakeholders. Effective school leadership requires a clear, future-oriented vision (Axiom 1) that provides a roadmap for the school community's goals and aspirations. School leaders play a crucial role in articulating this vision and ensuring it is effectively communicated to all stakeholders (Axiom 2). By clearly communicating the vision, school leaders foster alignment, inspire motivation, and enhance stakeholder engagement. This alignment of vision and communication not only strengthens organizational unity (Anggorowati et al., 2020) but also promotes a shared commitment to achieving educational objectives. Effective communication ensures that everyone—from teachers to parents to community members—understands the school's direction and their role in contributing to its success. Thus, this paper proposes that school leaders articulate a clear, future-oriented vision and communicate it effectively with all stakeholders.

Axiom 2. Effective school leaders are conversationalists. Effective school leadership requires a multifaceted approach, with the ability to engage in meaningful dialogue and foster open communication being a critical component (Wenning & Vieyra, 2020). School leaders who adopt a conversational style of leadership can create an environment conducive to collaboration, problem-solving, and continuous improvement (Ross & Cozzens, 2016). A conversational approach to leadership also allows school leaders to effectively communicate the school's vision, mission, and goals, ensuring alignment and buy-in from all stakeholders (Anggorowati et al., 2020). By fostering open dialogue, leaders can gather feedback, address misunderstandings, and make adjustments to better meet the needs of the school community. Effective conversational skills enable school leaders to better understand the needs and perspectives of their stakeholders, including students, teachers, parents, and the broader community. Through active listening and thoughtful questioning, leaders can identify and address concerns, while also generating ideas and solutions that resonate with those they serve. Principals who build trusting relationships and engage in shared leadership practices are more likely to positively impact school climate, teacher efficacy, and student achievement (Ross & Cozzens, 2016). Ultimately, effective school leaders recognize the power of conversation as a tool for driving school improvement and fostering a positive, collaborative environment. Through the development of strong communication skills and a commitment to meaningful dialogue, school leaders can become catalysts for change and champions of student success. In this case, this study assumes that effective school leaders are conversationalists.

Proposition 2. School leaders provide instructional support and maintain open communication with teachers about teaching strategies to enhance student academic performance. Supporting teachers with instructional guidance and maintaining open communication are essential responsibilities of school leaders (Anggorowati et al., 2020). Instructional support (Axiom 3) involves providing educators with the tools, resources, and professional development opportunities needed to enhance teaching effectiveness and improve student outcomes. Open communication (Axiom 2) fosters transparency, collaboration, and trust within the school community. When leaders actively engage in dialogue with teachers about teaching strategies, student progress, and professional growth, they create a culture of continuous improvement and shared responsibility for student success. This collaborative approach not only strengthens instructional leadership but also promotes a positive school culture where innovation and excellence thrive. Hence, this paper proposes that school leaders provide instructional support and maintain open communication with teachers about teaching strategies to enhance student academic performance.

Axiom 3. Effective school leaders are good instructors. Strong and effective school leaders can significantly impact the overall performance and effectiveness of a school (Döş & Savaş, 2015). Effective school leaders are not only good administrators, but they are also excellent instructors who can support and empower their teaching staff to deliver high-quality instruction (Ross & Cozzens, 2016; Rashid & Latif, 2021). One of their key responsibilities is to create an environment that fosters growth and development for both teachers and students. Effective school leaders understand the crucial role that teacher efficacy plays in student achievement, and they work diligently to cultivate a sense of collective efficacy among their teaching staff (Rashid & Latif, 2021). By encouraging shared leadership practices and empowering teachers to make decisions related to their professional skills, effective school leaders can motivate and inspire their teachers to deliver more effective instruction (Rashid & Latif, 2021; Ross & Cozzens, 2016). In addition to supporting their teaching staff, effective school leaders also play a direct role in the delivery of instruction within their schools. School leaders must demonstrate quality leadership behaviors that are consistent throughout the school and community, in order to build trust and support from various stakeholders (Ross & Cozzens, 2016). Effective school leaders not only manage the day-to-day operations of the school, but they also actively participate in instructional activities, such as monitoring staff, providing feedback, and allocating resources to support teaching and learning (Döş & Savaş, 2015). Therefore, it can be assumed that effective school leaders are good instructors.

Proposition 3. School leaders ensure the optimal utilization of resources, directing them towards achieving the school's goals and objectives. Effective school leaders prioritize the optimal utilization of resources to support the school's goals and objectives (Villanueva et al., 2021). A clear strategic vision (Axiom 1) guides leaders in making informed decisions about resource allocation, ensuring that financial, human, and material resources are directed towards initiatives that align with the school's educational goals and objectives. Efficient resource management (Axiom 4) involves strategic planning, budget oversight, and accountability measures to maximize the impact of resources on student learning and school improvement efforts. By responsibly managing resources, leaders enhance organizational efficiency, promote sustainability, and

strengthen the school's capacity to achieve its educational goals effectively. With this in mind, this paper proposes that school leaders ensure the optimal utilization of resources, directing them towards achieving the school's goals and objectives.

Axiom 4. Effective school leaders are efficient resource managers. School principals, in their capacity as leaders, are responsible for ensuring that their schools achieve a high level of performance by optimizing the utilization of available resources. They are expected to oversee the smooth and efficient functioning of their schools, which includes managing both human and material resources (Karataş, 2019). Skilled leaders are better equipped to navigate the complex and competing demands of school management, as they possess the necessary skills to prioritize tasks, allocate resources, and foster a supportive work environment (Prastiawan et al., 2020). Furthermore, effective school leaders are skilled at allocating their time and energy towards activities that directly contribute to school success. This may involve carefully selecting and replacing teachers, frequently monitoring staff performance, and providing additional resources and support to teachers (Döş & Savaş, 2015). By prioritizing these activities, effective school leaders can foster a culture of excellence and efficiency within their institutions. This, in turn, contributes to the overall effectiveness of the school and the satisfaction of both the teaching staff and student population (Abu-Hussain, 2014). Thus, it means that effective school leaders are efficient resource managers.

Proposition 4. School leaders adapt innovative instructional practices and support teachers' professional development to improve student achievement. Innovation in instructional practices and ongoing professional development are key strategies for improving student achievement (Ross & Cozzens, 2016). Effective school leaders (Axiom 3) encourage teachers to innovate by adopting new teaching methods, integrating technology, and adapting curriculum to meet the diverse needs of students. Supporting professional development (Axiom 5) ensures that educators have the knowledge, skills, and resources to implement effective instructional strategies and respond to evolving educational challenges. By investing in teachers' professional growth and fostering a culture of innovation, leaders empower educators to deliver high-quality instruction that enhances student engagement, learning outcomes, and overall academic success. Taking this into consideration, this paper argues that school leaders adapt innovative instructional practices and support teachers' professional development to improve student achievement.

Axiom 5. Effective school leaders are adaptive to changes. In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the role of school leaders has become increasingly vital in navigating the complexities and challenges that arise. Effective school leaders are those who possess the ability to adapt to the changing needs of their institutions, students, and communities. Adaptive leadership is a crucial component of effective school leadership. Adaptive leaders recognize that traditional approaches to leadership may not be sufficient to address the complex and often unpredictable nature of educational environments (Khan, 2017). Instead, they embrace a mindset of flexibility, innovation, and a willingness to take calculated risks (Lowder, 2009). Effective adaptive school leaders understand the importance of empowering their teams and fostering an environment of trust. By empowering individuals to engage in adaptive practices, these leaders can cultivate a

culture of innovation and resilience within their schools. Furthermore, adaptive leaders must be willing to confront challenging circumstances and initiate adaptive strategies in response to the unique needs of their organizations. By embracing an adaptive approach, effective school leaders can navigate the turbulence of educational change and lead their institutions towards transformative growth and innovation (Klerk & Palmer, 2021). Adaptive leaders understand that the solutions of the past may not be sufficient to address the challenges of the present, and they are willing to explore new strategies and approaches to problem-solving (Khan, 2017). Thus, effective school leaders are adaptive to changes.

Proposition 5. School leaders foster a positive culture of open communication among teachers and efficiently manage financial, human, and material resources.

A positive organizational culture and efficient resource management are interrelated components of effective leadership (Döş & Savaş, 2015). Open communication within an organization fosters a positive culture by building trust, encouraging collaboration, and promoting transparency. School leaders (Axiom 2) cultivate an environment where open communication among teachers promotes collaboration, shared decision-making, and continuous improvement in teaching practices. Strong communication builds trust, enhances teamwork, and strengthens relationships within the school community. Concurrently, leaders ensure efficient resource management (Axiom 4) by strategically allocating financial, human, and material resources to support educational priorities and operational needs. By fostering a culture of communication and responsible resource stewardship, leaders create a supportive and productive school environment where every stakeholder contributes to achieving the school's mission and goals effectively. Thus, this paper finally proposes that school leaders foster a positive culture of open communication among teachers and efficiently manage financial, human, and material resources.

Conclusions

Effective school leadership in educational institutions revolves around five core elements: **dynamic adaptability, resourceful management, instructional competence, visionary thinking, and engaging communication**. Dynamic leaders flexibly navigate changes, ensuring the school remains responsive and innovative. Resourceful leaders efficiently manage financial, human, and material resources to support educational goals. Instructional leaders focus on high-quality teaching and learning, fostering continuous professional development. Visionary leaders set clear, compelling goals, guiding the school community towards a shared future. Engaging leaders foster a positive school culture through open, transparent communication, building trust and collaboration among stakeholders. The synergy of these elements forms the cornerstone of effective school leadership, fostering excellence through visionary goals, supportive environments, and innovative practices. Hence, the theory is termed as **DRIVE Theory of Effective School Leadership**.

Figure 2. DRIVE Theory of Effective School Leadership

The findings of this study have significant implications for various aspects of education. For practices, the DRIVE Theory emphasizes the need for school leaders to adopt core elements such as dynamic adaptability, resourceful management, instructional competence, visionary thinking, and engaging communication. By focusing on these elements, school leaders can develop effective practices that foster positive school environments and enhance student outcomes. Continuous professional development and collaboration among staff are essential to creating a culture of innovation. In terms of policy, the study advocates for reforms that prioritize effective school leadership as a critical component of educational improvement. Policymakers should develop frameworks that support leadership training and evaluation aligned with the DRIVE Theory's principles, ensuring that adequate resources are allocated to leadership development initiatives. Additionally, the findings encourage the recognition and rewarding of effective leadership practices to promote sustainable school improvement. Regarding existing theories, this study contributes to the discourse in educational leadership by addressing theoretical gaps and proposing a comprehensive framework that integrates various leadership dimensions. The DRIVE Theory encourages

researchers to further explore the interplay between different leadership aspects and their impact on school effectiveness, inviting a re-evaluation of traditional leadership models to better reflect the complexities of modern educational environments. Overall, the implications of this study highlight the crucial role of effective school leadership in driving meaningful change within educational systems.

Recommendations (Theory Validation)

This validation process will employ a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods to gather data from stakeholders in top-performing schools within Region VII - Central Visayas. As a methodology for theory validation, the study will utilize interviews with students, teachers, and administrators to explore their perspectives on each proposition of the D.R.I.V.E. Theory. These interviews will provide qualitative insights into how dynamic adaptability, resourceful management, instructional competence, visionary thinking, and engaging communication manifest in their school environment. Additionally, Likert scale questionnaires will be administered to stakeholders for propositions related to communication strategies and instructional support, aiming to gauge perceptions and attitudes towards these aspects of effective school leadership. Document analysis will complement these methods, focusing on propositions concerning visionary thinking and adaptability by examining school documents, strategic plans, and policies. Participants will be selected from the top five performing schools in each division based on their academic excellence and leadership in educational initiatives. Ethical considerations will ensure participant confidentiality, voluntary participation, and informed consent throughout data collection. Data obtained from audiotaped interviews, questionnaires, and document analysis will be analyzed using appropriate qualitative and quantitative methods. Results for each proposition will be presented and discussed separately, providing insights into the alignment of findings with the D.R.I.V.E. Theory's propositions and offering recommendations for enhancing educational practices and leadership strategies in Region VII - Central Visayas.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In alignment with ethical standards, this study did not involve human participants, as its focus was primarily on developing a theoretical framework. No personal data or direct human interactions were required. Consequently, approval from an ethics review board was unnecessary for this research. Moreover, all sources utilized in forming the axioms and propositions were properly cited, ensuring academic integrity and respect for intellectual property. The researchers also maintained objectivity throughout the analysis and formulation of the proposed theory.

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